

Determination of Shelf Life of Packaged Water in Selected Water Packaging Factories, Ota, Ogun State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT:

Water is critical for human survival. Therefore, its quality and safety are non-negotiable, especially in packaged forms like sachets and bottles. However, when human beings consume unsafe water, they become prone to waterborne diseases which could result in deaths. Therefore, this study investigated the shelf life of packaged water from four selected water packaging factories in Ota, Ogun State, Nigeria, labeled samples A, B, C and D. Selected physicochemical and microbial analyses were carried out on water samples monthly for three months according to American Public Health Association standards, to assess any changes over the three months. Results indicated that while most samples met the World Health Organization (WHO) minimum standards for drinking water quality, still notable variations were observed as the months of analyses progressed. Sachet water samples exhibited more significant reduction in physicochemical and microbial quality compared with bottled water samples. This study concludes that sample A recorded the best results comparatively. Also, shelf life of sachet water is relatively shorter compared with bottled water, with a suggested storage period of three months under typical room and tropical conditions to ensure safety and quality. These findings emphasize the need for more quality control measures, better storage practices and frequent factory monitoring to ensure safety of packaged drinking water. The study recommends that regulatory agencies better enforce existing water packaging guidelines, while packaging factories should also adopt improved packaging and handling processes to enhance shelf life of their products.

Keywords: Shelf life, Packaged water, Physicochemical, Microbial, Water quality.

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INTRODUCTION

Packaged drinking water can be defined as water filled into hermetically sealed containers of various compositions, forms and capacities (sachets, bottles and water dispensers), which are safe for direct consumption [1]. Furthermore, packaged water has evolved from a relatively obscure product to one of the most popular beverages in the world. Historically, packaged water can be traced in Europe to as far back as the 16th Century when natural mineral water was sold in glass bottles and was considered a luxury beverage for special occasions [2]. Similarly, the first bottled mineral water for public consumption in the United States of America (USA) was in the second half of the 18th century [3], while industrially carbonated water was first patented in 1806 [4]. According to [5], the consumption and use of packaged water in countries such as South Africa, Nigeria, Greece, Canada, Mexico and the USA has experienced a significant increase at least in the last sixteen years.

According to Okeola *et al.*, [6], all potable water in sachets or bottles, distributed and made available for sale to be consumed by the public are considered as packaged water. Furthermore, packaged water may be obtained directly from municipal systems, boreholes, wells, natural springs or any other water source deemed to be of sanitary quality, safe and fit for human consumption [7]. Generally, this type of packaged water is described as natural packaged water, but the type of packaged bottled water where inorganic metal salts (coagulants) are added for the purpose of treatment is called mineralized packaged water [8]. Fadipe *et al.*, [9], reported that although access to potable water in Nigeria has consistently increased, especially in the last decade, still the quality of available drinking water has deteriorated because of the noticeable presence of toxic elements which pose serious health problems to consumers.

Consequently, this low quality in available pipe-borne water has made packaged water very popular among the populace and is arguably the major source of drinking water, especially in Nigerian urban centers [10]. Therefore, this continued use and consumption of packaged water requires constant regulation, monitoring and supervision such that the public will not be at risk of waterborne diseases. This is even more important because scientific studies such as [11, 12, 13] have reported that most regulatory agencies in Nigeria have not performed satisfactorily in enforcing international best practices on the water packaging factories that package and sell water to the public. This reported laxity usually provides opportunity for unscrupulous water packaging factories to exploit and sell unsafe water to the public.

Therefore, this study seeks to bridge this gap by investigating the shelf life of packaged water being sold in selected water packaging factories in Ota community, Ado Odo Ota local government, Ogun State, Nigeria in order to determine whether the quality of these water samples deteriorate over time or not. This is important because a reliable and sustainable supply of potable water is highly essential for promoting healthy living, since unsafe water predisposes consumers to life threatening diseases such as typhoid, cholera and dysentery [14].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The equipment used for this study were; atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AAS), laboratory weighing scale, laboratory oven, conical flask, autoclave, evaporating dish, laboratory thermometer, laboratory incubator, test tubes, agar plates, volumetric flask, laboratory beaker and extraction cup.

The materials used for this study were; packaged water samples (sachet and bottled water samples) labeled samples A, B, C and D, which were obtained directly from four different water packaging factories all located in Ado Odo-Ota local government, Ota, Ogun State, Nigeria. According to [15], Ota in Ogun State falls within the 6.69° N and 3.23° E geographical coordinates and has the tropical rainforest climate, having two major climatic conditions (rainy season which occurs for seven months between April and October; and the dry season which occurs for four months between November and February). Ota is home to an estimated 163,783 residents who are mostly civil servants, factory workers, artisans and small business owners.

Suffice to mention that Ota is usually described as the industrial hub of Ogun State, because it is home to several multinationals that do business in Nigeria and Sub-Saharan Africa. The large number of residents living in the city who require clean, safe and wholesome water for their daily activities (mostly dependent on packaged water) and the recent cholera outbreak in Lagos and Ogun States, Nigeria, therefore necessitated the conduct of this study, in a bid to protect public health and preserve communal wellbeing as well.

After purchase, the packaged water samples were immediately transported to the central research laboratory of Bells University of Technology for storage and laboratory analyses. While inside the laboratory, care was taken to ensure that the water samples were kept inside a clean, spacious and well-ventilated open cabinet in the laboratory. This was done to ensure that the water samples were all kept away from any direct source of contamination and to ensure that they were stored under room temperature throughout the three months (April, May and June) of the study. Furthermore, the packaged water samples were taken at intervals of four weeks for the laboratory analyses of their physical, chemical and microbial parameters, making a total of twenty four separate analyses for sachet water and bottled water (twelve for sachet water and twelve for bottled water respectively).

The laboratory analyses of the physical, chemical and microbial parameters of the packaged water samples were all carried out according to the American Public Health Association (APHA) standards [16]. The parameters analyzed were; pH, Electrical Conductivity, Turbidity, Nitrate, Phosphate, Calcium, Magnesium, Potassium, Hardness, Colour, Taste, Sodium, Manganese, Lead, Aluminium, Biochemical Oxygen Demand, Iron, Odour and Coliform Count. Also, the results obtained from the laboratory analyses were compared with the World Health Organization (WHO) [17] for compliance with minimum drinking water quality standards.

Laboratory Analyses of Physical and Chemical Parameters

pH: The pH values were measured through the pH meter that had been calibrated as shown in Figure 1. Packaged water samples were measured into the extraction cup, while the pH meter probe was also rinsed using the distilled water. This was then standardized using a buffer solution of known concentration. Furthermore, adequate quantity of the aliquot sample was measured into a beaker so that full immersion of the pH probe can occur, while also making sure that the pH meter was switched on. The values displayed on the pH meter were observed to ascertain the degree of acidity and alkalinity.

Electrical conductivity: This was also measured with the electrical conductivity meter having a probe as shown in Figure 2. The probe was immersed in the packaged water samples, while the voltage was subsequently applied between the two electrodes in the probe. The noticeable drop or reduction in the voltage applied between the electrodes is often caused by the impurities in the water samples and this was used to calculate the conductivity value of the water samples.

Turbidity: This was determined with the aid of turbidity meter as shown in Figure 3 having optical scattering detection capacities for reliable and fast measurements. This was carried out by measuring packaged water samples into a small glass basin connected electronically to the turbidity meter. The turbidity meter was previously turned on and left to measure accurately.

Nitrate: Concentrated H_2SO_4 of 150mL measurement was used to dilute 25g of phenol with an extra H_2SO_4 of 5mL concentration added before stirring. This solution was then heated using a hot water bath and subsequently allowed to cool. Packaged water sample of 100mL measurement was mixed with another Ag_2SO_4 solution of 100mL, to prevent chloride interference. Thereafter, $AgSO_4$ of 4.4g was poured into 1L of distilled water for dilution with a prepared silver sulphate solution. Also, nitrogen of 100mg/L was used to dissolve 0.722g anhydrous KNO_3 in distilled water of 1L to prepare the nitrate stock solution. Furthermore, the packaged water sample was neutralized up to pH 7 with dilute NaOH before filtration. The water samples were then poured into a beaker, they were allowed to dry by evaporation, while the residue was mixed with 2.0mL phenoldisulfonic acid reagent with the glass rod to dissolve the solids. The mixture was dissolved with concentrated ammonia of 6mL and distilled water of 20mL, till a deep yellow colour developed. The solution was dissolved in distilled water and poured into a volumetric flask of 50mL. The solution was allowed to cool and nitrate results were read from the graph.

Figure 1. pH Meter in Use for Analyses

Figure 2. Electrical Conductivity Meter in Use for Analyses

The water samples were then poured into a beaker, they were allowed to dry by evaporation, while the residue was mixed with 2.0mL phenoldisulfonic acid reagent with the glass rod to dissolve the solids. The mixture was dissolved with concentrated ammonia of 6mL and distilled water of 20mL, till a deep yellow colour developed. The solution was dissolved in distilled water and poured into a volumetric flask of 50mL. The solution was allowed to cool and nitrate results were read from the graph.

Figure 3. Turbidity Meter in Use for Analyses

Phosphate: Packaged water samples were poured into an extraction cup, with 5 mls of Murphy and Riley solution added as well. Furthermore, distilled water of 10 mls was added to the mixture, with the solution allowed to cool after few minutes. Thereafter, a bluish colour developed and the blue colour solution was analyzed for phosphate using the AAS at 882nm wavelength.

Calcium, Potassium and Sodium: Packaged water samples were measured into an extraction cup and analyzed for the presence of Calcium, Potassium and Sodium using the AAS.

Hardness: This was done by complexometric titration. The packaged water samples were titrated with a standard solution of ethylene diamine tetra acetic acid (EDTA) (complexing agent). The

detection of hardness was carried out through the copper electrode and copper-EDTA. The total sum of the EDTA complexable ions were determined by calculating to the nearest mg/l.

Colour: The photo electric method was used for this experiment. Standard colour solutions were measured into volumetric flasks of 100ml which resulted in a range from 10 to 200 Hazen units. The standard measured quantities were diluted with filtered distilled water to remove turbidity. The calibration graph that connects optical density with Hazen units was used, while the water samples were filtered using the laboratory glass fiber filter paper to remove any remaining turbidity. Optical density was then measured with AAS at a wavelength between 385 and 470nm, while the colour of the water samples were recorded to the nearest 5 Hazen units from the calibration graph.

Taste and Odour: This was carried out simply by tasting and smelling the packaged water samples under room temperature repeatedly to determine whether they were objectionable or unobjectionable.

Biochemical oxygen demand: Laboratory bottles of analytical grade were first used to incubate the packaged water samples in the dark. The noticeable reduction in the concentration of dissolved oxygen during incubation was used to confirm the value of biochemical oxygen demand as presented in Equation 1

Biochemical oxygen demand:

$$D1 - D5 \quad (1)$$

D1 = Initial dissolved oxygen of packaged water sample

D5 = Final dissolved oxygen of packaged water sample after five days of incubation

Heavy Metals Analyses

Concentrated nitric acid of 5mL was poured into packaged water sample of 250mL in a beaker and then stirred. This solution was heated with a hot plate till the volume noticeably reduced to 20mL. Thereafter, de-ionized water was used for diluting to 50mL and then poured into a tagged sample bottle. Stock solutions were then prepared in 1L flask through dissolution of specific amount of salts and which were made up to 1000mL. Furthermore, serial dilution was carried out from the stock solution for analysis, while the final concentrations of Magnesium, Manganese, Lead, Aluminium and Iron were determined in ppm using AAS as shown in Figure 4.

Bacteriological Analyses

The most probable number (MPN) of coliform counting was adopted for this experiment. Distilled water of 9mL was measured into six test tubes, while Eosine Methylene Blue (EMB) agar measuring 3.8g was added to the distilled water. Thereafter, the test tubes and EMB solution were placed inside autoclave for 45minutes to achieve sterilization. After sterilization, 1mL of packaged water sample was measured into the first test tube with sterilized distilled water of 9mL to make 10^{-1} dilution and then shaken well. Mixed 10^{-1} dilution of 1mL was measured into the second test tube (10^{-2} dilution) also. This procedure was continued for the remaining four test tubes by measuring 1mL of previous test tube and pouring it into the 9mL diluents that were next. The final dilution of bacteria cells were taken as the 10^{-6} dilution. Furthermore, packaged water sample measuring 1mL was collected from each test tube and poured into plates having EMB agar and then covered. These were subsequently left in the incubator as shown in Figure 5 for 72 hours, while the Escherichia Coli colonies that developed were determined through the colony counter.

RESULTS

The results of all the packaged water samples analyzed are shown in Tables 1 to 4 and Figures 6 to 9. The results showed that all the water samples (A, B, C and D) mostly satisfied the physical, chemical and microbial parameters analyzed according to the standards of the World Health Organization [17]. However, the pH (6.5 to 8.3) and Electrical Conductivity (97 to 157mg/l) values of

all samples fluctuated throughout the months of analyses, especially the June results of Sample B in Table 2. The fluctuation noted in the pH and Electrical Conductivity may also be the reason why the values of Calcium, Sodium and Potassium noticeably increased as the months progressed as well. The values of Colour for all the samples remained within the minimum permissible limit of 5 throughout, because the water samples have gone through the process of treatment for consumption, making the water samples wholesome for consumption.

Figure 4. Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer in Use for Analyses

Figure 5. Incubator in Use for Analyses

Furthermore, the values of Colour obtained could also be useful for the explanation of the values of Turbidity. The Turbidity values for all samples were relatively low (2.1 to 3.4mg/l) since the packaged water samples have been adequately treated for consumption. Also, the results obtained for heavy metals as shown in the Tables and Figures showed that Lead and Manganese were below 1mg/l throughout the three months, while Magnesium, Aluminium and Iron were mostly above the 1mg/l threshold. Similarly, the microbial results obtained showed that the values of coliform count remained undetectable per 100mL of water samples analyzed throughout the duration of analyses. Thus, the packaged water samples are fit for drinking and they do not pose any public health danger to the consumers.

Table 1. Results of Packaged Water from Sample A in mg/l

Parameters	April		May		June	
	Bottled Water	Sachet Water	Bottled Water	Sachet Water	Bottled Water	Sachet Water
pH	7.1	7.2	6.7	6.5	7.0	7.2
Electrical Conductivity	97	99	105	109	120	124
Turbidity	2.1	2.0	2.7	2.8	3.1	3.3
Nitrate	1.9	1.7	2.5	2.4	4.5	4.4
Phosphate	2.3	2.5	2.7	2.6	3.6	3.8
Calcium	1.0	1.2	2.3	2.5	5.8	6.0
Magnesium	0.7	0.4	0.7	0.6	0.56	0.6
Potassium	4.2	4.0	2.9	3.1	4.44	4.5
Hardness	130	127	129	129	139	134
Colour	1.2	1.3	1.3	1.4	2.6	2.8
Taste	Unobjectionable	Unobjectionable	Unobjectionable	Unobjectionable	Unobjectionable	Unobjectionable
Sodium	5.1	5.0	5.9	5.3	3.6	3.8
Manganese	0.9	0.8	0.5	0.6	0.32	0.4
Lead	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2
Aluminium	0.7	0.9	2.3	2.4	2.43	2.5
Biochemical Oxygen Demand	0.5	0.4	2.8	2.9	1.53	1.8
Iron	0.8	0.9	3.1	3.2	2.22	2.4
Odour	Unobjectionable	Unobjectionable	Unobjectionable	Unobjectionable	Unobjectionable	Unobjectionable
Coliform count (cfu)	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.3	0.2

Figure 6. Results of Sample A

Table 2. Results of Packaged Water from Sample B in mg/l

Parameters	April		May		June	
	Bottled Water	Sachet Water	Bottled Water	Sachet Water	Bottled Water	Sachet Water
pH	6.9	6.7	7.7	7.9	8.1	8.3
Electrical Conductivity	155	157	138	142	128	141
Turbidity	2.3	2.2	3.8	3.9	3.1	3.3
Nitrate	2.7	2.5	4.2	4.4	5.2	5.5
Phosphate	1.1	1.3	4.4	4.8	4.2	4.4

Calcium	1.9	1.7	2.9	3.1	6.1	5.9
Magnesium	0.06	0.8	1.0	1.3	0.8	0.6
Potassium	2.8	2.9	3.65	3.8	3.3	3.5
Hardness	118	123	121	131	114	128
Colour	3.3	3.4	2.9	2.7	2.9	2.7
Taste	Unobjectionable	Unobjectionable	Unobjectionable	Unobjectionable	Unobjectionable	Unobjectionable
Sodium	4.71	4.8	4.6	4.7	3.6	3.8
Manganese	0.9	0.7	0.74	0.74	0.18	0.23
Lead	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.2
Aluminium	1.7	1.9	2.9	2.8	2.3	2.5
Biochemical Oxygen Demand	1.6	1.5	1.2	1.5	1.5	1.4
Iron	1.7	1.9	1.0	1.3	2.7	2.9
Odour	Unobjectionable	Unobjectionable	Unobjectionable	Unobjectionable	Unobjectionable	Unobjectionable
Coliform count (cfu)	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.2

Figure 7. Results of Sample B

Table 3. Results of Packaged Water from Sample C in mg/l

Parameters	April		May		June	
	Bottled Water	Sachet Water	Bottled Water	Sachet Water	Bottled Water	Sachet Water
pH	7.2	6.9	7.5	7.3	7.7	7.9
Electrical Conductivity	114	111	138	135	127	130
Turbidity	1.6	1.8	2.4	2.3	2.5	2.6
Nitrate	1.9	2.1	3.0	3.1	2.2	2.1
Phosphate	2.5	2.7	2.7	2.9	4.3	4.2
Calcium	2.0	2.0	4.3	4.5	5.5	5.1
Magnesium	0.7	0.9	1.0	1.0	1.2	1.4
Potassium	1.4	1.1	2.5	2.7	3.6	3.9
Hardness	127	115	151	145	141	148
Colour	0.8	0.9	1.1	1.0	0.9	0.8
Taste	Unobjectionable	Unobjectionable	Unobjectionable	Unobjectionable	Unobjectionable	Unobjectionable
Sodium	2.6	2.8	2.9	3.1	2.8	2.6
Manganese	0.9	0.7	1.0	1.1	0.12	0.10
Lead	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.2

Aluminium	0.6	1.0	2.1	2.2	3.5	3.7
Biochemical Oxygen Demand	0.7	0.8	0.1	0.001	0.94	0.99
Iron	1.10	1.12	0.8	0.6	1.6	1.4
Odour	Unobjectionable	Unobjectionable	Unobjectionable	Unobjectionable	Unobjectionable	Unobjectionable
Coliform count (cfu)	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.4

Figure 8. Results of Sample C

Table 4. Results of Packaged Water from Sample D in mg/l

Parameters	April		May		June	
	Bottled Water	Sachet Water	Bottled Water	Sachet Water	Bottled Water	Sachet Water
pH	6.9	7.0	7.5	8.0	7.7	7.9
Electrical Conductivity	138	141	136	149	132	135
Turbidity	2.6	2.9	2.6	2.8	3.4	3.1
Nitrate	3.1	3.2	3.5	3.7	4.8	4.6
Phosphate	3.7	3.9	3.4	3.1	4.0	4.2
Calcium	5.3	5.1	2.4	2.1	5.4	5.2
Magnesium	1.4	1.1	1.6	1.9	0.5	0.8
Potassium	2.6	2.3	3.4	3.65	2.6	2.0
Hardness	159	151	132	121	141	134
Colour	2.8	3.0	2.6	2.9	1.8	1.6
Taste	Unobjectionable	Unobjectionable	Unobjectionable	Unobjectionable	Unobjectionable	Unobjectionable
Sodium	8.4	8.9	4.8	4.6	4.9	4.2
Manganese	1.6	1.9	0.5	0.74	0.25	0.18
Lead	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
Aluminium	3.2	3.4	2.5	2.1	2.4	2.1
Biochemical Oxygen Demand	0.30	0.32	1.4	1.8	1.1	1.2
Iron	1.58	1.56	1.6	1.0	2.4	2.2
Odour	Unobjectionable	Unobjectionable	Unobjectionable	Unobjectionable	Unobjectionable	Unobjectionable
Coliform count (cfu)	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.4

Figure 9. Results of Sample D

DISCUSSION

The observed values of pH for all the samples as presented in Tables 1 to 4 and Figures 6 to 9 are in agreement with the findings of Olaniyan *et al.*, [18], as the study also reported that water samples which have received sufficient amounts of coagulants during treatment would largely fall within the permissible limits as seen in Table 5.

Table 5. WHO (2022) Parameters for Drinking Water Quality

S/N	Parameters	Permissible limits (mg/l)
1	pH	6.5 – 8.0
2	Turbidity (NTU)	5
3	Electrical Conductivity	<1000
4	Nitrate	10
5	Phosphate	5
6	Calcium	20
7	Magnesium	10
8	Odour	Unobjectionable
9	Taste	Unobjectionable
10	Sodium	<200
11	Lead	0.1
12	Hardness	60 – 120
13	Colour	5
14	Aluminium	<0.2
15	Manganese	0.1
16	Potassium	12
17	Iron	0.3
18	Biochemical oxygen demand	<5
19	Coliform count (cfu)	<10

This could also explain the obviously low values of Turbidity and Colour for all the samples, because according to [18] when water samples have been properly treated, especially during coagulation and flocculation, the organic materials and total solids (total dissolved solids and total suspended solids) which could raise the values of Turbidity, Colour and Nitrate, would have been eliminated. However, the results also showed that as the months of analyses progressed, pH, Turbidity, Colour and Electrical Conductivity values slightly increased as well, especially for sachet water samples. Although, the values for all the samples were still within the minimum standards of the WHO for drinking water quality as seen in Table 5 for the three months of analyses.

Furthermore, the results obtained for Hardness as shown in the Tables and Figures ranged between 114 and 159mg/l with the highest value of 159mg/l recorded in April for Sample D under the bottled water category. This according to [19] may have been caused by the deposition of Magnesium and Calcium through the pipe networks used to transport the packaged water samples before they are bottled or bagged. Subsequently, this may also be responsible for the unstable values of Calcium, Magnesium, Manganese and Iron in the packaged water samples analyzed throughout the period of analyses. Odour and Taste in water are often caused by high temperature, reduced dissolved oxygen and other objectionable matter that have entered the water source. When dissolved oxygen is greatly deficient, water becomes toxic and becomes a breeding ground for harmful microorganisms [20]. Water that will be used domestically or consumed should not have objectionable Odour and Taste as seen in Table 5. Since the water samples have been treated before packaging, the unobjectionable results obtained for Odour and Taste as seen in Tables 1 to 4 and Figures 6 to 9 are thus expected, meaning that the packaged water samples all passed the minimum requirements for drinking water.

Furthermore, the values of heavy metals (Magnesium, Manganese, Lead and Iron) for all the samples as shown in the Tables and Figures generally fell within the permissible limits for drinking water throughout the months of analyses. Since heavy metals are undesirable in food, water and other consumable items, it is therefore crucial to ensure they are adequately removed from drinking water. This is because according to [17], when heavy metals are consumed in drinking water above the allowable limit, mental retardation in infants, cancer and death in adults may result. Furthermore, the values observed for the coliform count (mostly undetectable) as presented in Tables 1 to 4 and Figures 6 to 9 revealed that all the packaged water samples met the minimum requirements as presented in Table 5. This means that the consumers are not at risk of waterborne diseases such as dysentery, cholera and typhoid fever caused by bacteria in water. Generally, the results obtained for this study showed that the water samples met the minimum requirements for drinking water throughout the three months of analyses. However, variations in the results were noted as the duration of analyses progressed, especially in the sachet water samples.

CONCLUSION

This study concludes that the packaged water samples all satisfied the minimum requirements for drinking water quality throughout the three months of storage and laboratory analyses. However, the study also concludes that as the study duration progressed, sachet water samples generally recorded noticeable quality reduction, especially sachet water samples of sample B. Furthermore, this study concludes that out of the four samples studied, sample A presented the best results relatively. This study therefore recommends that regulatory agencies should do more in the enforcement of existing water packaging guidelines, while packaging factories should also adopt improved packaging and handling processes to enhance shelf life of their products. This will effectively prevent the noticeable decline observed in the sachet water samples as the months progressed, especially in sample B. Further studies can consider extending the study duration beyond three months (to cover both the dry and rainy seasons), so as to further examine how the values of the water samples (especially heavy metals and microbial values), will either decrease or increase over time.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

No conflict of interest

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